

STUDY OF THE MICROMECHANIC BEHAVIOR OF SHORT-FIBER- REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE OF RECYCLED HIGH DENSITY POLYETHYLENE USING FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced composites of recycled high density polyethylene were simulated with a micromechanic unit cell. The micromechanical effect of fiber reinforcement was studied in terms of the stress distribution between the fiber and the matrix using finite element method. Effects of fiber aspect ratio and orientation on the composite behavior were investigated. A stress partition ratio was introduced to evaluate the load bearing capability of fibers in a composite. As the fiber aspect ratio increased, stress partition ratio of the unit cell increased. Stress partition ratio decreased as the fiber orientation angle increased.

INTRODUCTION

A typical problem associated with plastic recycling is that recycled plastics have inferior properties compared with their virgin counterparts. Experimental study has been carried out to reinforce the recycled plastic with short glass fibers. The reinforced thermoplastic composite has properties superior to plastics without reinforcement. However, a comprehensive understanding of the role of fibers in the composite is essential to optimize the behavior of the composite, and to save time and cost for composite materials development.

Investigations were conducted on the reinforcing effect of different fibers on composites. In a study conducted by Hwang and Gibson [1], finite element analysis was used to predict the fiber interaction and interfacial effects on composite damping. The results showed that fiber interaction affected the damping of discontinuous fiber composites, and that damping can be improved by increasing the fiber end gap or by decreasing the fiber aspect ratio. In the research by Hom [2], three-dimensional finite element calculations were performed to predict quantitatively the tensile behavior of a metal matrix composite reinforced with aligned short fibers. The results showed that the material's load carrying capacity in a direction transverse

to the fiber was significantly lower than that along the fiber direction. In the study by Sun and Chen [3], finite element analysis was used to understand the elastic-plastic response of laminated thermoplastic composite plates and shells. In an investigation by Kwon and Byun [4], a model and its finite element formulation were developed to analyze fiber-reinforced composite structures with some local damages such as matrix cracks. In their study, the stresses acting in fibers and the stresses acting in the matrix were computed directly using theoretical models.

Andrews *et al.* [5] studied the deformation micromechanics in high-modulus fiber composites. It was shown that the distribution of strain can be mapped along a fiber and the interfacial shear stress can be calculated from the strain in fibers in a single-fiber composite. Nassehi *et al.* [6] conducted a finite element simulation of the micromechanics of interlayered polymer/fiber composites. It was shown that the use of interlayer was more beneficial at higher fiber volume fractions in enhancing the energy absorbing capabilities of a polymer/fiber composite.

An analytical model was presented by Carman and Reifsnider [7] to predict the point-wise stresses in the fiber and the matrix including the stress state at fiber ends. The stiffness tensor of the composite was calculated by globally averaging the approximate stresses in the representative fiber and matrix of the composite. Bigelow [8] developed an analytical micromechanics-based strength prediction methodology to predict failure of notched metal-matrix composites.

No study has been conducted on the micromechanic behavior of short fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composite of recycled high density polyethylene. In this study, finite element analysis was performed to study micromechanic behavior of the thermoplastic composite and the role of glass fibers in reinforcing recycled plastics. The effect of fiber reinforcement was studied in terms of the stress distribution between glass fiber and high density polyethylene (HDPE) matrix on a micromechanic unit cell.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, a unit cell [9] consisted of a single glass fiber and high density polyethylene (HDPE) matrix. The material properties of the constituents are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the constituents

Material	E-fiberglass	HDPE
Density (g/cm ³)	2.565	0.96
Tensile strength (MPa)	3448.3	30.3
Tensile modulus (GPa)	72.41	1.03
Poisson's ratio (ν)	0.22	0.34

A finite element analysis software Algor for microcomputer was employed. The general assumptions involved in the analysis were: (i) The embedded fiber was transversely isotropic and the surrounding matrix was isotropic; (ii) The constituents in the composite exhibited linear elastic behavior; (iii) The fiber/matrix interface was a "perfect" bond. A very low external stress of 0.138 MPa was used to maintain the validity of the assumptions.

In this study, von Mises stresses were used on both fiber and matrix. The stress field in the unit cell was defined by Eqn (1).

$$\bar{\sigma}_i = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \sigma_i dV = \frac{1}{V} \left[\int_{V_f} \sigma_i dV + \int_{V_m} \sigma_i dV \right] \quad (1)$$

where σ_i is the stress in the unit cell as a function of x, y and z coordinates, V is the total volume of the unit cell, V_f and V_m are the volume of fiber and matrix, respectively. The volume-average stresses $\bar{\sigma}_{fi}$ in the fiber and $\bar{\sigma}_{mi}$ in the matrix are defined by Eqn (2) and (3).

$$\bar{\sigma}_{fi} = \frac{1}{V_f} \int_{V_f} \sigma_i dV \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{mi} = \frac{1}{V_m} \int_{V_m} \sigma_i dV \quad (3)$$

To measure the load-bearing capability of fibers, a stress partition ratio of fiber to matrix was introduced for the composite unit cell.

$$SPR = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{fi}}{\bar{\sigma}_{mi}} \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{fi}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{mi}$ are average stresses in fiber and matrix, respectively. From the view point of composite strengthening, a larger stress partition ratio would lead to a higher strength for the composite.

Figure 1. Cutaway view of a micromechanics unit cell for composites of recycled high density polyethylene reinforced by glass fibers.

Fig. 1 shows a cutaway diagram of the composite unit cell used in the analysis. The fiber length was kept identical as 101.6 mm for all models and the radius of the fiber varied from 0.635 mm to 6.35 mm. The percentage of the fiber was 6.98%. Uniaxial loads of 0.138 MPa were added along the fiber direction on the right end of the model. The left end surface of the unit cell was fully constrained. To investigate the effect of fiber orientation on the stress distribution in the fiber and the matrix, geometrical models were created with various

angles between the fiber axis and the tension load axis. While calculating the stresses in both fiber and matrix, the whole unit cell was divided into 10 slices along the fiber direction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MODEL VALIDATION

To validate the finite element models and processor, a comparison was made between the predicted elastic properties with a theoretical model by Carman and Reifsnider [7] and predictions for short fiber composite in this work. The properties of the constituents used by Carman and Reifsnider are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Material properties of constituents in validation model

Material	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio, ν	Density (g/cm ³)
Epoxy resin	2.0005	.35	1.25
Steel	190.0000	.30	7.8

A finite element model consisting of a single steel fiber and its surrounding epoxy resin was created with the same conditions as in the analysis by Carman and Reifsnider, with the modeling method and linear processor in this study. The fiber aspect ratio was 50 and the volume fraction of fiber in the model was 6%. The result ($E=6.4$ GPa) by Algor finite element processor agreed reasonably well with the theoretical prediction verified by experimental results ($E=6.6$ GPa) from Carman and Reifsnider [7].

EFFECT OF FIBER ASPECT RATIO (a)

Fig. 2 shows the variation of average stress in glass fiber with the distance from the left end of the unit cell for three different fiber aspect ratios. The stress in the fiber increased with increasing fiber aspect ratio. The maximum stress occurred at the left end of the fiber and the stress decreased as the distance increased. The stress became consistently higher inside the fiber as the aspect ratio increased. This observation implies that for the best strengthening of the composite, a large fiber aspect ratio is desirable.

The stress distribution in the matrix is presented in Fig. 3 for three fiber aspect ratios. As the fiber aspect ratio increased, the stress in the matrix generally decreased. The stress in the matrix was higher at both ends of the model and reached a minimum and relatively stable value in the middle of the model. This result shows that the fiber with larger aspect ratio carries a higher load in the composite, which results in lower stress in the matrix. Moreover, the magnitude of stress in matrix is much lower than that in fiber.

To demonstrate the load bearing capability of the glass fiber, stress partition ratios due to various fiber aspect ratios were calculated along the distance from the left end of the model, as shown in Fig. 4. The stress partition ratio was lower at both ends of the fiber and was maximum in the middle of the composite unit cell. A stress partition ratio was more stable and consistently larger in higher fiber aspect ratio model than in lower fiber aspect ratio.

To further study the effect of fiber aspect ratio on the stress distribution in the composite and the strengthening effect of the fiber, average stress in fiber and that in matrix in the middle

of the unit cell were calculated. Fig. 5 shows the variation of fiber stress and matrix stress in the middle of a unit cell with fiber aspect ratios. The stress in fiber increased as the fiber aspect ratio increased. After the fiber aspect ratio reached approximately 20, the stress in the fiber tended to be saturated. The stress in the matrix decreased with an increasing fiber aspect ratio up to approximately 20. Then the slope of change became very flat. Moreover, the stress in the high density polyethylene matrix was much lower than that in the glass fiber.

Figure 2. Variation of stress in fiber with the distance from the left end of the unit cell for fiber aspect ratios of 8, 16 and 80.

Figure 3. Variation of stress in matrix with the distance from the left end of the unit cell for fiber aspect ratios of 8, 16 and 80.

Figure 4. Variation of stress partition ratio with the distance from the left end for fiber aspect ratios of 8, 16 and 80.

Figure 5. Variation of fiber stress and matrix stress in the middle of the unit cell with various fiber aspect ratios.

The stress partition ratio in the middle of the unit cell is shown in Fig. 6. The stress partition ratio increased with fiber aspect ratio up to 20 and then leveled off. The maximum stress partition ratio in the composite of high density polyethylene reinforced with glass fiber was close to 73. A conclusion can be drawn that the fiber aspect ratio of 20 for glass fiber provides the most effective strengthening of the composite. Moreover, stress partition ratio can be conveniently used to evaluate the load bearing capability of reinforcing fibers.

EFFECT OF FIBER ORIENTATION ANGLE

It was concluded from the above study the stress partition ratio was effectively used to explain the strengthening role of fibers in the composite. Thus, the effect of fiber orientation on the micromechanic behavior of the composite will be discussed in terms of stress partition ratio.

The orientation angle is defined as 0° when the fiber is aligned along the loading axis and 90° when the fiber is perpendicular. As the fiber orientation angle increased, the stress in the fiber decreased and the stress in the matrix increased. Fig. 7 depicts the variation of stress partition ratio with fiber orientation angle. The stress partition ratio decreased as the angle increased and reached the lowest point when the fiber orientation angle was approximately $A=75^\circ$. It is concluded that the fibers oriented in the tension load direction provide the maximum strength for the composite.

Figure 6. Variation of stress partition ratio in the middle of the unit cell with fiber aspect ratios.

Figure 7. Variation of stress partition ratio in the middle of the unit cell with fiber orientation angles.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions were made according to the micromechanic analysis on glass-fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composite of recycled high density polyethylene using finite element method.

1. The geometrical model and Algor processor are adequate for the micromechanic analysis of the thermoplastic composites.
2. A stress partition ratio has been introduced successfully to evaluate the load bearing capability of fibers in the composite.
3. As the fiber aspect ratio increased up to 20, the stress in the fiber increased, the stress in the recycled HDPE matrix decreased, therefore the stress partition ratio increased. The aspect ratio of 20 for glass fiber provides the most effective strengthening of the composite.
4. Stress partition ratio decreased as the fiber orientation angle increased. Fibers aligned in tension load direction provided the best load carrying capability.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Financial supports from the Illinois Department of Energy and Natural Resources through the Office of Solid Waste Research at University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, and from the Council for Faculty Research through Office of Research and Grants at Eastern Illinois University are greatly appreciated.

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